

Wind Potential Assessment and Optimization of Wind Turbine Blade for District of Naukundi Balochistan Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates assessment of wind potential and the performance of wind turbine blade for district Naukundi a blade is design and simulated in software named Q-blade the parameters are chosen keeping in view the weather condition of Naukundi (hard, dusty and dry area of Balochistan). The average wind speed of Naukundi is about 6.4 m/s and suitable length of blade should be 3-5m here the length 2.85m gives the results that are satisfying about 9.8KW.

INTRODUCTION

Power has been extracted from the wind over hundreds of years with historic designs, known as windmills, constructed from wood, cloth, and stone to pump water or grind corn. Historic designs, typically large, heavy, and inefficient, were replaced in the 19th century by fossil fuel engines and the implementation of a nationally distributed power network. A greater understanding of aerodynamics and advances in materials, particularly polymers, have led to the return of wind energy extraction in the latter half of the 20th century.

Wind power devices are now used to produce electricity, commonly termed wind turbines [1, 2]. Balochistan, one of the largest provinces in Pakistan, has an area of 347,190 square kilometers (sq. km), which is 43.6% of Pakistan's total land. It lies between 28.4907°N latitude and 65.0958°E longitude. The majority of the area is covered with hills and mountains [3]. Unfortunately, many parts of Balochistan are facing an Energy crisis due to the unavailability of power. The population of this area is scattered and spread over large areas.

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Many areas, such as Nukundi Jewni ormara of Balochistan, have a larger potential of energy production when it comes to wind energy. Here our focus is on the location of Naukundi, a dusty and dry area. The average wind speed of said area is 6.4 m/s, which shows a very decent geographical location for installation of wind turbine. In any country the economic growth is considered as backbone for the progress of a region, and for that, energy plays an important role. Balochistan has the best spots for wind power within Pakistan, especially in the remote areas of Nokkundi. The high demand for renewable energy increased over the year in developed and underdeveloped countries worldwide. Wind energy is considered a viable energy source. Pakistan, with an important geographical landscape, in the world has significant wind energy potential, especially in the coastal areas of Balochistan [4]. This literature review focuses on wind potential assessment and the optimization of wind turbine blades in the district of Nokkundi, Balochistan. Nokkundi, which is located in the southwest of Pakistan close to the Iran border, has some unique wind characteristics that make it an ideal place for wind energy project installation. Figure 1 shows the average yearly precipitation of Nukandi.

Figure1: Naukundi, Pakistan Average Yearly Precipitation
WIND POTENTIAL IN PAKISTAN

Pakistan is recognized as a country with vast wind energy potential. According to the Alternative Energy Development Board (AEDB), regions in Pakistan, particularly Balochistan, have wind resources that could generate about 50,000 MW of electricity. The stats show that if this region is properly utilizing its windy areas like Naukundi the energy deficit may overcome up to some extent windmills are still looking for their installation, especially Nokkundi, which

remains underexplored. Many dedicated researchers from Balochistan have recently worked on the subject and produced some quality results on wind turbine blades and evaluated the wind power potential of different geographical areas of Pakistan.

WIND POTENTIAL ASSESSMENT FOR REGION NOKKUNDI

The potential of wind can be assessed by measurement of wind speed, wind direction, angle of attack, and other meteorological data for a specific period. For Nokkundi, studies such as those by demonstrate the need for localized data collection to accurately estimate the wind resource [5]. The wind data of some areas of Balochistan and suggested that this region could support wind turbines. It was very difficult to obtain reliable wind data for the area like because of its geographical location and factors such as the lack of infrastructure and continuous monitoring, and the influence of seasonal variations on wind patterns. Moreover, an assessment using remote sensing technologies such as LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) or ground-based anemometer installations can be very useful in this case for better results [6].

FAVORABLE CONDITIONS FOR WIND TURBINE INSTALLATION

The wind speeds in Balochistan could exceed 7 m/s, which is favorable for large-scale wind energy production [4]. The wind data, however, needs to be analyzed in more detail for specific locations like Nokkundi to determine their suitability for wind turbine installation. Corresponding to a 15 GW power generation potential capacity at a highly competitive cost from clean energy resources. Balochistan, a province of Pakistan, has a population of around 20 million. The people of this part of the country are suffering from an energy crisis. However, the region has a coastal belt of 770 km, and wind energy (wind turbines) can resolve said issue for the population. it is observed that the disparity between energy demand and supply has widened in most South Asian countries, affecting the region’s economic development. The people of Balochistan are living below the standard line. Fossil fuels, which are considered to be a source of energy not very affordable for the people living in Balochistan because of their cost. Renewable energy (RE) sources, especially wind energy, can resolve such a problem to extent. This natural asset (wind energy) can be used to satisfy the energy gap and prevent the energy dilemma of potential demand in Balochistan. Wind velocity in NokKundi is recorded as 16.5 Km/h at an altitude of around fifty meters during the year. Such analysis shows the fastest winds throughout the summer season, if we take a look to our neighboring south Asian countries, we found lot of research work on wind potential over there this is the need of time that wind energy potential to be developed at the region level as

documented by many published research papers Researchers investigated the wind [2].

WIND TURBINE BLADE OPTIMIZATION

The most important part for windmill installation is to design a Wind turbine blade which has more efficient than before. An optimized wind turbine blade is the need of Nokkundi region, as the blade directly influences energy capture. Here, the factors that are most important for our work are local wind speed, turbulence intensity, and season. For the case of Nokkundi, the following optimization process can be considered.

AIRFOIL DESIGN

we used the airfoil (NACA 0013), depicted in figure 2, and also used a circular airfoil for initial two sections.

Figure 2: Airfoil design for proposed blade

BLADE LENGTH AND EFFICIENCY

The length of the blade is important as a blade with a longer area can capture more wind energy and produce better results as compared to one with a shorter area. Studies such as those by Liu et al. suggest that a length of 30–50 meters may be ideal for medium-wind speed locations, but this depends heavily on local wind patterns [2]. In Nokkundi, average wind speeds in Naukundi is 6.4 m/s, which shows moderate-sized blades can produce high results as far our results are concern we had made a blade of 2.85m for achieving better results.

BLADE PITCH CONTROL

Another factor that affects the efficiency of the wind turbine is pitch control. Studies by [10] show that pitch-controlled blades allow the turbine to adapt to changing wind speeds, which is essential for regions with fluctuating winds like Nokkundi. The optimization of pitch control can improve turbine efficiency even in wind speed variation.

WIND ENERGY PROJECT OF BALOCHISTAN

The government of Balochistan is looking into the matter seriously as the energy crisis is causing damage to the growth of the province. Many wind energy projects have been proposed or are under consideration; some of them may also

be under development in Balochistan. The Jhok Ibrahim Wind Power Project and the Gharo Wind Corridor is an example as per Pakistan Wind Energy Atlas (2013), the wind potential in the district of Nokkundi has yet to be fully explored. Initial assessments suggest that Nokkundi's proximity to the Iranian border and its location in the desert region could provide steady wind resources, albeit with the challenge of ensuring consistent wind speed data over extended periods. Iqbal et al., suggested that the integration of modern forecasting systems, such as numerical weather prediction models (NWP), could significantly improve the reliability of wind data for areas like Nokkundi. By combining these models with local observations, more accurate predictions of wind speed and direction can be made, facilitating the proper design and optimization of wind turbines for the region [7 - 9].

RESULTS

Q-Blade software is used for blade design and simulation. A complete package which has all the comforts for the blade design and simulation. Figure 3 gives the lift coefficient, drag coefficient and angle of attack. Figure 3 shows lift coefficient, drag coefficient and angle of attack. In figure 4, the polar view is shown. Finally figure 5 gives the results of BEM results of the proposed blade.

Figure 3: Curves of lift coefficient, drag coefficient and angle of attack

Figure 4: Polar view of model (NACA 0013)

Figure 5: BEM simulation analyzes results of (NACA 0013)

CONCLUSION

This paper presents the generation of wind turbine Blade design and simulation of such blade in Simulation Software known as Q-Blade. The aerodynamic performance of the designed blade was investigated using Q Blade's Lifting Line Theory (LLT) simulation. With the blade streamlines. 12 m/s was the inflow velocity used in the simulation. Under the given conditions, the rotor showed good efficiency with a power coefficient (C_p) of 0.344 and a reported power output of 9.386 kW. These results demonstrate the aerodynamic viability of the blade design.

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